

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN THE NUN RIVER OILFIELD COMMUNITIES AND THEIR NEIGHBOURS

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Comparative Analysis, Quality Of Life, Nun River Oilfield, Neighbours, and Communities.

Abstract: This Paper Compared Quality Of Life In The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours, And Determines The Factors Causing Variations. It's Difficult To Effectively Measure Qol, So The Human Development Index (Hdi) Was Used As The Measurement Criteria. Different Factors Such As Education, Income And Occupation Were Examined To Ascertain How They Influence Qol. The Study Was Carried Out In Fifteen (15) Communities In Southern Ijaw Local Government Area Of Bayelsa State. Primary Data Was Collected Through Survey Instrument; A Questionnaire Was Administered On 398 Respondents Selected Through The Simple Random Sampling Technique. Data Were Analysed Using Both Descriptive And Statisticaltools. The Results Showed That The Indicators Used In The Study Significantly Affected Qol In Individuals And Communities; And Established That Qol Varied Between The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours. Descriptive Data Showed That 43% Of Respondents In The Oilfield Communities Rated Qol As Good, While Only 22% Of Respondents In Neighboring Communities Rated Qol As Good. Similarly, The Result Of Anova Statistical Test Showed That F-Ratio Calculated 101. 812 Were Greater Than Tabulated Value Of 3.84 At Significant 0.005. Also, The P-Value 0.000 Was Less Than The Significant Level 0.05, Suggesting That There Is Significant Variation In Qol Between The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbors. Sequel To The Findings, We Suggest Governments Deliberate Investment In Infrastructure: Healthcare, Education And Sanitation In Rural Communities; Provide Capacity Building Programmes For Rural Dwellers To Enhance Their Skills, Knowledge And Socioeconomic Status.

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Introduction

Although Quality Of Life (Qol) Has Been The Direction Of Researchers In Both Developed And Developing Countries, Yet A Universally Acceptable Definition Is Far-Fetched (Du And Peter, 2016). Hence, The First Step In The Development Of The World Health Organization Quality Of Life (Who Qol) Was To Posit A Definition Of The Concept. According To Who, Qol Is The Individual's Perception Of Their Position In Life In The Content Of The Culture And Value Systems In Which They Live And In Relation To Their Goals, Expectations, Standards And Concern. From The Foregoing, Qol Is A Broad Raging Concept Incorporating In A Complex Way The Individual's Physical Health, Psychological States, Level Of Independence, Social Relationships, Personal Beliefs And Their Relationships To Salient Features Of The Environment. Sirgy (2001) Attempting To Incorporate Varieties Of Viewpoints Of Qol, Defined Qol As A General Comfort That Entails Both Objective And Subjective Assessments Of Physical, Material, Social And Emotional Well-Being As Well As Purposeful Activities, All Linked To A Personal Set Of Standard. Hence, According To The Author Qol Is Both Objectively As Subjectively Assessed.

Ortegem And Verhofstadt (2015) Noted That, The Subjective Indicators Focus On Pleasure As

Key To Human Happiness And Satisfaction As Qol , And The Objective Indicators Focus On The Health Status, Housing, Income, Educational Attainment And Nutritional Levels. The Primary Focus Of This Paper Is On The Objective Indicators Of Qol Such As Income, Education And Employment But Not To The Exclusion Of Some Subjective Indicators. Kele (2012) Noted That Qol Is Largely Affected By Certain Factors; Housing, Leisure And Recreation, Economic Stability, Neighbourhood Environment, Job Opportunities, Public Goods And Services. He Further Noted That Community's Qol Connotes a Group of Socioeconomic and Environmental Factors/Indicators Such As Crime, Health, Jobs, Educational Attainment, Justice, System and Recreation That Adds to the Desirability and Livability of a Community. According To Boroah, Dineen And Lynch (2011), The Variations In Income, Employment, Educational Attainment, Availability And Access To Basic Amenities Determines Differences In Qol Experiences Among Individuals And Communities; In This Case The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours.

The Nun-River Oilfield Communities Are Host To International Oil Companies E.G. Spdc Which Activities Holds Negative Consequences To The People And Environment. However, In A Bid To Ameliorate The Plight Of Host Communities Caused By Their Multiple Disadvantage They Suffer As A Result Of Small Size And By Devastation From Oil/Gas Activities, Industry

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Operators Undertake Several Development Projects As Part Of Them Csr. It Is Hoped That These Csr Projects Enhance The Qol Of The Citizens Of Host Communities. It Is Against This Backdrop That This Paper Is Aim To Undertake A Comparative Analysis Of Qol In The Two Groups Of Rural Communities, I.E. Oil/Gas Bearing Community And Their Neighbouring Non-Oil/Gas Bearing Communities, With Key Objectives: To Assess The Socioeconomic Characteristics Such As Income, Education And Employment Of The People In The Sampled Communities, And Ascertain Spatial Variations In Qol Between The Two Sets Of Communities. The Research Hypothesis States That There Is Significant Variation In Qol Among The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours.

Literature/Conceptual Review

According To Maxwell, Chukwuemeka, Nneka, And Kelechi (2014) Quality Of Life (Qol) Is A Multifaceted Concept, Which Encompasses Crucial Areas Such As Physical Health, Psychological Well-Being, Social Relationships, Economic/Income Status, Personal Beliefs And Their Relationship To Salient Features Of The Environment. Achieving A Better Quality Of Life (Qol) Is The Goal Of Every Economy Across The World (Mujib, Muhammad And Wisal, 2020). The Authors Further Noted That The United Nations (Un) In 2015 Introduced Sustainable Development Goals (Sdgs) For Their 2030 Agenda, Which Is Based On 17 Goals That Cover

An Array Of Socioeconomic, Equality, Health And Environment Issues. These Sdgs Focus On Those Dimensions Which Are Closely Connected With The Betterment Of The Qol.

The Concept Of Qol Is A Geographical Variable Condition As It Varies Not Only Between People, But Also Between Places, Basically Due To The Characteristics Of People And Places. As Noted By Bayode, Adewuni And Odunwole (2011), Environmental Quality, Social And Economic Conditions, As Well As Political Atmosphere Of Any Community Affect The Citizens' Quality Of Life. Akinyemi, Ononye, Popoola And Ilesanmi (2012) Argued That Consequent Upon The Availability Of Social Amenities, Demographic And Socio-Economic Dynamics, Qol Of One Community Ultimately Vary From Qol Of Another Community, Even Within Same Geographic Area. The Authors Further Stated That Qol In A Community With Enormous Natural Resources And Amenities Shows A Significantly Different Qol Constructed Compared To A Sterile Community. Similarly, Maheda (2014) Stated That Availability And Access To Different Resources And Basic Services Is Strategic In The Attainment Of An Enhanced Quality Of Life.

According To The United Nations Development Programme (Undp,1998), Qol Involves The Fulfillment Of Basic Needs Which Include Health, Education And Standard Of Living, While Sirgy Et Al (2004) Called It A Qualitative Measure Of Well-Being Which Include

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Consumers, Health, Social ,Economic And Physical Well-Being. Therefore, The Authors Stated That Qol Is A Subjective Measure, And To Empirically Measure It, The Best Proxy Is The Human Development Index (Hdi). Boncinelli And Casini (2014) Posited That The Task Of Determining The Level Of Qol Includes The Identification Of Set Of Indicators, Which Include Health, Income, Education, Employment, Politics, Environment And Infrastructure, And There Determinants Are Not Available In Every Community, Are Measured Using The Hdi Approach. The Human Development Index (Hdi) Initiated By the United Nations In 1990 Is Used To Intake The Development Status Of A Country. Hdi Is Used To Measure Different Development Indicators Such As Education Level, Life Expectancy And Standard Of Living. Majeed (2019) Argued That Income Per Capita Is The Best Measure For Qol. Besides Income, Education Is The Major Determinant Of Qol, Which Is Was Highlighted By Anand And Sen (1999).

Education Enhances Qol By Increasing The Knowledge And Skills Which Support Access To Employment/Jobs And Enhances Productivity (Majeed 2019). The Author Further Noted That Education Also Equips With The Power To Decide And The Freedom To Choose Among Options. Though, The Relationship Between Education And Quality Of Life Can Be Complex And Influenced By Various Factors, Including Socioeconomic Status, Access To Resources And

Individual Characteristics (Nussbaum, 2011). Thus Qol Is Improved Through The Availability Of Better Facilities, Such As Health, Education, Employment Opportunity As Well As Income (Asongu, 2013).

Senlier, Yidiz And Aletes (2008) Undertook A Comparative Study Of Qol In Selected Kocaeli Communities In Turkey And European Cities. In The Contrast, Essential Determinants Of Qol Such As, Employment, Education, Income, Housing Etc. Were Measured Using The Hdi Measurement Technique. A Total Of 3000 Perception Surveys Were Made And Fretor And Repression Analysis Were Used To Analyse Data Collected Through The Survey Method. The Result Of The Analyses Showed Significant Variation In Qol In The Various Cities.

The Study Area

The Study Area Has A Total Of Fifteen (15) Communities, Which Comprised Of Ten (10) Bearing Communities In The Nun River Oil Field And Five Neighbouring Communities, Which Are Non-Oil/Gas Bearing; All In Southern Ijaw Local Government Area Of Bayelsa State. The Local Government Has A Total Area Of 2, 68 Kilometers, With A Population Of About 319,413 According To Npc, 2006. The Sampled Communities Are Shown In the Map Of Southern Ijaw L.G.A. Sampled Communities Had A Total Population Of 54,982 People At 2019. The Geographical Coordinate Of The Central Point Of The Study Area Which Is Oporoma Is In Latitude $4^{\circ}48'17''$ North And Longitude $6^{\circ}04'44''$ East.

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The Area Lies In The West Equatorial Climatic Region Of The Niger Delta, It Is Typically A Humid Tropical Climate Characterized By Lying Rainfall And High Temperature (Gobo 1998). The Temperature Of The Area Rages Between Is And 32°C With Little Monthly Variations. The Vegetation Cover Of The Study Area And That Of The Bayelsa State Is Typical Of The Fresh Water Areas Characterized By Grasses And Trees, And Surface Soil Showing Moderate Suitability For Crop.

The Study Area Is Nets In Natural Resources Which Include Oil/Gas With Oil Wells In Most Communities And Projects Crisis-Crossing The Area. The Major Economic Activities Of The Area Are Agriculture, Including Fishing, Family, Forestry/Lumbering, Gathering Of Wild Forest Products And Tapping Of Palm Wine And Brewing Of Local Gin Are The Primary Economic Activities Is The Areas. Allison – Oguru, Zuofa and Berepubo (1999).

Materials and Methods

As Earlier Stated The Research Covered Ten (10) Oil/Gas Bearing Communities And Five (5) Neighbouring Non-Oil/Gas Bearing Communities, Totally Fifteen (15) Communities, All In The Southern Ijaw Local Government Area

Of Bayelsa State. The Total Projected Population Of The Research Area Was 103,608 And Sample Size For The Study Was 398, Which Was Determined Using The Taro Yamene Formula For Determining Sample Size. Consequently, A Set Of 398 Structured Questionnaires Was Administered To The Selected Respondents, Who Were Mostly Household Heads. The Survey Instrument (Questionnaire) Was Administered Directly By Hand To The Respondents To Fill And Return Same. Data Obtained Were Analysed Using Both Descriptive Statistics And Analysis Of Variance (Anova), Been Adopted To Test The Only Hypotheses Which State That There Is Significant Variation In Qol Among The Nun-River Oil/Field Communities And Their Neighbour. The Research Used Mainly Primary Data And Direct Physical Observation Of Available Infrastructure Amenities Of Communities.

Results and Discussions

This Section Provides A Clear Understanding Of The Research Findings And Their Significance As Well As Enlightens The Audience On How The Results Are Presented To Achieve The Objectives Of The Study. Analyses Of Data Were Presented Under The Following Sub-Headings:

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Educational Qualification of Respondents.

Fig 1: Educational Qualifications of Respondents from Nun River Oilfield Communities and Their Neighbours. Source: Field Survey 2025

As Shown In Fig 1, In the Nun River Oilfield Communities 22 (10%) Of The Respondent’s Highest Educational Qualification Was Informal Education, 43 (20%) Had Fslc, 72 (33%) Had Waec, 38 (17%) Of The Respondents Had Ond/Nce, 30 (14%) Of The Respondents Had Hnd/B.Sc, 10 (5%) Of The Respondents Had M Sc, and 3 (1%) Of The Respondents Had Phd. On The Other Hand, In the Neighbouring Communities 7(6%) Of The Respondents Had Informal Education, 14 (12%) Had Fslc, 40 (33%) Had Waec, 33 (27%) Had Ond/Nce, 24 (20%) Had Hnd/Bsc, 1 (0, 8%) Of The Respondents Had M.Sc and 1 (0.8%) Of The Respondents Had Phd As Their Highest Educational Qualification. Personal Observation Showed That Respondents With Higher Educational Qualification Indicated Higher Qol Rating. Nussbaum (2020) Posited That Individuals With Higher Educational

Attainment Tend To Report Better Qol, Citing Factors Such As Improved Economic Stability, Better Health Outcomes And Enhanced Personal Growth, Satisfaction And Social Participation.

Income Level of Respondents

Table 1: Monthly Income of Respondents from Nun River Oilfield Communities and Their Neighbours.

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Oil Field Community

S/N	Income Earned	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
1	Less Than 70,000	86	39
2	70,000 -79,000	12	6
3	80,000 - 89,000	60	27
4	90,000 - 99,000	24	11
5	100,000 + Above	38	17
	Total	220	100

Neighbouring Community

S/N	Income Earned	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
1	Less than 70,000	10	8
2	70,000 -79,000	16	13
3	80,000 - 89,000	42	36
4	90,000 - 99,000	22	18
5	100,000 + above	30	25
	Total	220	100

Source: Field Survey 2025

Results from the Nun River Oilfield Communities on Monthly Income Showed That 86 (39%) Earned Less than ₦70, 000, 12 (6%) Earned Between ₦70, 000 – ₦79, 000, 60 (27%) Earned Between ₦80, 000 – ₦89, 000, 24 (11%) Earned Between ₦90, 000 – ₦99, 000 And 38(17%) Earned ₦100, 000 and Above. On The Other Hand, In Neighbouring Communities 10 (8%) Earned Less than ₦70, 000, 16 (13%) Earned Between ₦70, 000 – ₦79, 000, 42 (36%) Earned Between ₦80, 000 – ₦89, 000, 22 (18%) Earned Between ₦90, 000 – ₦99, 000 And 30 (25%) Earned ₦100, 000 and Above.

Source: Field Survey 2025

Studies Have Showed That Income Level Impacts Qol. According To Kahneman And Deaton (2010), Higher Income Can: Provide Basic Needs, Such A Food, Shelter And Healthcare; Offer Financial Security And Enable Access To Education, Leisure And Resources. However, The Authors Noted Not The Relationship Income And Qol Is Complex Because Excessive Income Does Not Always Translate To Greater Happiness.

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Occupation Of Respondents

Fig 2: Occupations of Respondents from Nun River Oilfield Communities and Their Neighbours.

Source: Field Survey 2025

This Figure Showed That 102 (46%) Of The Respondents in the Nun River Oilfield Communities Were Farmers, 36 (16%) Were Fishers, 34 (15%) Were Traders, 26 (13%) Of The Respondents Were Civil/Public Servants, 5(2%) Were Company Workers; Artisans Were 10(5%), 5 (2%) Were Clergy and Others Were 2 (0.9%) Of Respondents. In The Neighbouring Communities 34(28%) Of The Respondents Were Farmers, 24 (20%) Were Fishers, 27 (23%) Were Traders, 26 (22%) Were Civil/Public Servants and 9 (7%) Were Artisans.

Results From Cross Sectional Data Analysis Revealed That Respondents In Government

Employment Evidenced Better Qol Rating Compared To Others Engaged In The Non-Formal Sector. The Occupation Of An Individual Is Part Of His Everyday Life, Thus, There Is No Gainsaying That The Nature Of The Occupation Or A Change Of It Would Affect The Individual's Well-Being And Inadvertently The Qol. Maxwell, Chukwuemeka, Nneka And Kelechi (2014), Concluded That Occupational Factors Had Negative Impact On The Qol Of Respondents In The Non-Governmental Sectors Than Their Counterparts In Government Sector Of The Economy.

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Essential Goods and Services

Fig. 3: Essential Goods and Services in Nun River Oilfield Communities and Their Neighbours. Source: Field Survey, 2025

Relating To the Degree of Impact of the Availability of Essential Goods and Services on Qol Variations, Results in Fig 3 Revealed That in Nun River Oilfield Communities 130 (59%) Of Respondents Disagreed To the Assertion That the Availability of Essential Goods and Services Have Had a Positive Impact on Quality Of Life (Qol), 70 (32%) Agreed, 14(6%) Strongly Disagreed and 6(3%) Strongly Agreed. In The Neighbouring Communities 79(66%) Disagreed, 16(13%) Agreed, 21(18%) Strongly Disagreed,

And 4(3%) Strongly Agreed That The Availability Of Essential Goods And Services Have Positive Impacts On Quality Of Life In Their Communities.

Qol Rating In Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours

A Comparison Of Qol Rating Between The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours Was Determined, The Rating Ranged From Poor, Good And Very Good, And The Distributions Are Presented In Fig 4;

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Fig. 4: Qol Rating In Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours.

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Results in Fig 4 Showed That in Nun River Oilfield Communities 78(35%) Of The Respondents Rated Qol as Poor, 86(39%) Rated Qol as Good, 13(6%) Rated Qol as Very Good and 43(20%) As Very Poor. In The Neighbouring Communities the Results Showed That 51(42%) Rated Qol as Poor, 23(19%) Rated Qol as Good 9(8%) Of Respondents Said Qol Was Very Good and 37(31%) As Very Poor.

Reports From The Oporoma Cluster Development Board Evidenced That

Infrastructural Development Projects Has Been Undertaken By Spdc As Part Of The Company's Csr To Host Communities. Table 1 Shows Some Of Such Projects Undertaken From 2011-2019 In Various Nun River Oilfield Host Communities That Are Covered By This Research. (See Appendix 1). **Csr Intervention in Nun River Oilfield and Neighbouring Communities**

A Comparison of the Impact of Csr Interventions in the Nun River Oilfield Communities and Their Neighbours Was Undertaken, and the Distributions Are Presented In Fig 5

Fig 5: Beneficial Intervention Of Csr In Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours.

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Results Showed That In The Nun River Oilfield Communities 147(67%) Of The Respondents Said That Csr Interventions Projects Undertaken By The Spdc Was Beneficial, And 73(33%) Said That They Were Not Beneficial. In The Neighbouring Communities The Results Showed That Only Negligible 6(5%) Of Respondents Said That Csr Interventions Were Beneficial And

114(95%) Of Respondents Said Csr Interventions Were Not Beneficial To Their Community.

Testing Of Hypothesis

The Single Hypothesis Of The Study Stated Thus: There Is Significant Variation In Qol Between Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours

Table 2: Analysis Of The Variation (Anova) Between The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbours

Description	Sum Of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	22.402	1	22.402	101.812	.000
Within Groups	25.964	338	.220		
Total	48.367	339			

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The Result Of The Anova Test In The Table 2 Revealed That The Value Of The F-Ratio Calculated 101.812 Are Greater Than The Tabulated Value 3.84 At 5% Level Of Significant. Secondly, The P-Value 0.000 Is Less Than The

Significant Level 0.05. Therefore, The Null Hypothesis Was Rejected And The Alternative Accepted Which States That There Is Significant Variation In Qol Between Nun River Oilfield Communities And Neighbouring Communities.

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Conclusion

The Indicators Of Qol Used In This Study Were Found To Have Significantly Affected Qol In Individuals And Communities. Comparative Analysis Of Qol Showed Variations Between The Nun River Oilfield Communities And Their Neighbouring Communities As Explained In Fig.5, Which Illustrates Qol Rating Of Various Communities As Well As The Results Of The Statistical Analysis In Table 2. Results From The Descriptive Data Showed That 43% Of Respondents In The Nun River Oil Field Communities Rated Qol As Good, While Just 22% Of Respondents In The Neighbouring Communities Rated Qol As Good. Secondly, Results Of The Statistics Analysis Established A Significant Variation In Qol Between The Two Sets Of Communities. This Aligns With The

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Result Of Akinyemi Et Al (2012) Who Concluded That Qol Vary From One Community To Another, Especially Due To Availability And Access To Social Amenities, Economy And Population Dynamics.

Recommendation

Following The Research Findings, We Underscore The Need For Deliberate Investment In Infrastructural Development Such As Healthcare, Education And Sanitation In Rural Communities; Provide Capacity Building Programmes For Rural Community Dwellers To Improve Their Skills And Knowledge As Well As Design And Implement Environmental Protection Measures To Mitigate The Impacts Of Teething Environmental Problems That Bedevils Rural Communities.

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Appendix

Table 2: Projects In Oporoma Cluster Development Board

S/ N	Communit y	Project Title	Start Date	Completi on	Proj ect Cost	Status
1	Oporoma	Completion Of Six Classroom Block	16 th Dec. 2011	2012	10,00 4,600 .00	Completed
2	Oporoma Marine	Building Of Landing Craft/Transportation	19 th Nov. 2013	2014	39,60 0,000 .00	Completed
3	Oporoma	Construction Of 127m X 6m Concrete Walkway At Ogboinbiriwater Front Road.	11 th Jan, 2018	10 th March, 2018	15,66 1,626. 75	Completed
4	Oporoma	Construction Of 183m X 6m Concrete Walkway With A Section Raised Walkway Floor Deputy Road.	14 th Jan, 2018	12 th March, 2018	22,91 0,039 .58	Completed
5	Oporoma	Construction Of 130m X 6m Concrete Walkway At Ogumeinpolo Road.	15 th Jan, 2018	14 th April, 2018	16,211 ,013.0 0	Completed

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6	Oporoma	Construction Of 107m X 6m Concrete Walkway At Highness Road.	25 th Jan, 2018	7 th April, 2018	14,14 4,580 .45	Completed
7	Oporoma	Construction Of 120m X 6m Concrete Walkway At Obolo Road.	25 th Jan, 2018	7 th April, 2018	14,761 488.0 0	Completed
8	Oporoma	Completion Of 2 Bedroom Bungalow (Doctors Quarters).	18 th Jan, 2018	20 th April, 2018	8,302 ,682.1 9	Completed
9	Onyoma	Construction Of 200m X 6m Concrete Walkway.	27 th Jan, 2018	2 nd April, 2018	24,01 5,096 .00	Completed
10	Luduon	Construction Of Cassava Processing Mill	12 th Dec. 2011	11 th March, 2018	1,695, 300.0	Completed
11	Luduon	Construction Of 50m X 4m Concrete Walkway.	18 th Jan, 2018		0 6,343 ,627.5 0	Completed

(Table 2 Continued)

S/ N	Community	Project Title	Start Date	Completi on	Project Cost	Status
12	Luduon	Provision Of Furnishing Of Corper's Lodge + Students Desk At Luke Primary School.	March,20 19		5,215,100 .00	Ongoing
13	Angiama	Completion Of Six Classroom Block.	24 th Jan, 2018	2 nd May, 2018	16,793,04 0.00	Comple ted
14	Obololi	Completion Town Hall.	26 th Jan, 2018	30 th May, 2018	9,836,32 5.45	Comple ted
15	Igeibiri	Completion Of Corper's Lodge	5 th Jan,2018	18 th Dec. 2018	9,541,11.2 5	Comple ted

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16	Aguobiri	Completion Of Six Classroom Block	Jan. 2018		9,774,950.00	Ongoing
17	Bolou-Aguobiri	Extension Of Two Classroom Block	21 st May, 2014	Stalled	3,784,278.00	70% Completed
18	Onyoma	Completion Of 12 Room Toilet With Water Facility.	March, 2019	May, 2019	3,483,088.00	Completed
19	Onyoma	Construction Of 75m X 4m Concrete Walkway.	March, 2019	May, 2019	7,451,544.00	Completed
20	Angiama	Construction Of 140m X 6m Concrete Road.	March, 2019	May, 2019	17,299,522.00	Completed
21	Angiama-Gbene	Construction Of 100m X 6m Concrete Road.	March, 2019	May, 2019	13,367,230.00	Completed
22	Osokama	Construction Of Water Project	17 th Dec. 2011	2012	5,000,000.00	Completed
23	Aguobiri	Construction Of A Block Of 2 Units Of 2 Rooms Toilets.	March, 2019		10,900,000.00	Ongoing
24	Igeibiri	Renovation Of Community Sch	March, 2019		15,491,107.00	Ongoing

Source: Oporoma Cluster Development Board, 202